

THE RELEVANCE OF HEGEL IN THE INDIA OF 2014-15

Dr. Sorab Sadri

Professor of Management Sciences and Director,
School of Business and Commerce, Manipal University Jaipur, India

Abstract

Georg Frederick Wilhelm Hegel (August 27, 1770 – November 14, 1831) was arguably one of the greatest philosophers who walked the face of this earth. Immanuel Kant who divided the world into the real world and the metaphysical world preceded him and first spoke of the dialectic. Hegel gave the world the first circular logic, which he also called the dialectic. This dialectic (to Hegel) consisted of thesis (the original idea) the antithesis (opposition to the idea) and the synthesis (the conclusion of the idea). In time, synthesis became thesis and the cycle continued. Hegel was the precursor of Marx from whom the concept of dialectic was borrowed and along with Engels, Marx gave the world dialectical materialism. All four of them were Germans! Today in India, we seem to swear by the supremacy of the state that would have been anathema to Hegel. He was perfectionist, an idealist, a philosopher rolled in one, and who championed the cause of the modern republic. It is at a time when the supremacy of the Indian state is being questioned by some protagonists, there is alleged fraud and blatant corruption in high places and the fight between the Judiciary and the Legislative wings of government which comes to the fore in an ugly manner and that we need to take a fresh look at Hegel. Instruments of state have been increasingly used to trouble political opponents. Development and education have been replaced by the doctrines of pseudo secularism and appeasement. Contradiction is writ large and real development is illusive. A frustrated Indian populace has overwhelmingly voted Narendra Modi into power and a new dawn of nationalism and attendant social identity is on the horizon. The Second Republic has indeed been born in India and Hegel was one man who championed the cause of the republic more than any other in his time. It is under such conditions that this paper is penned. The paper argues that while Hegel is still relevant as a universal thought leader the social reality of our times has forced the author to look beyond the Hegelian dialectic. It is here that the post 2005 works of Sadri, Sharma and Albuquerque clearly stand out.

Key words: synthesis, HEGEL, dialectic, philosophers

The Basics: Beginning with the dialectic for Hegel the thesis was man (read humankind) since man was made from the image of God. The antithesis was strife in the social community. The synthesis was the state, which he saw as the supreme perfection. Marx then took him on and stated that man was born in a state of nature so state was the thesis; social change (reform or revolution) provided the antithesis. The final liberation of MAN from all bonds (fetishes of society) was the synthesis. Hence, in his letter to his father Marx justifiably wrote “I found Hegel standing on his head and put him back on his feet”. [This was a critique of the resultant ideological aftermath of the French Revolution. It has witnessed the making of the Social Contract a la Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau.]. Many Leftists even today use the word dialectic loosely, but here they err. The dialectic is a form of logic that consists of two parts: (a) Unity in opposites e.g., man marries a woman; the beautiful lotus grows in a dirty pond. (b) Realty in contradictions e.g. we read better when we write with a white chalk on a black board. Hence, if a political sociologist were to try to understand the world as we see it he has to use the twin tools of unity of opposites and reality in contradiction. Objective social reality has compelled us to go beyond this Hegel-Marx-Leftist theme and the paper shall speak of this imperative later.

Hegelian Argument: Mark Twain is reported to have said that “whenever the literary German dives into a sentence that is the last you are going to see of him till he emerges on the other side of the Atlantic with a verb in his mouth”. Turgid prose aside, a successful exposition of Hegel’s conception of the state and the body politic, as it is articulated in his *Philosophy of Right*, must overcome several substantial obstacles, both ideological and philosophical. In the Western political tradition, there is a tendency to view the state primarily as an apparatus of control which guarantees individual rights, such as the right to property, and prevents the reversion of the community to chaos and the war “of every man, against every man”. This is the legacy of political theories like those of Thomas Hobbes and John Locke which view the state as the result of a contract: a conscious, rational decision by individuals to transfer their natural rights to a sovereign power in exchange for the protection of their lives and their personal property. To the liberal sensibility, the Hegelian state appears to be the antithesis of its contractarian counterpart. It seemingly denies liberal rights and demands, among other things, that individuals make their interests “subordinate to it and dependant on it”. As such, Hegel’s theory of the state is liable to draw hostile reaction. Indeed, Hegel’s characterization of the state has been referred to as many things: as a general model for totalitarianism according to Bertrand Russell, as the codification of the “god-state” by L.T. Hobhouse, as the cause of the death of virtue in twentieth century revolutionaries by Albert Camus, as an apology for Prussianism according to Karl Popper, and as a theoretical justification for imperialism according to Noam Chomsky.

Hegel’s view of law and ethics, involving as it does also his view on politics and history, is basically at variance with prevailing views, the concept of the state being that of a community rather than an institution (Anstalt). The failure to grasp this divergence of the concept of the state, as Hegel uses it, has been the source of most of the misunderstandings. For if the prevailing modern concept of the state as primarily a government, an institutional manifold comprising those who exercise command functions in the community is substituted for Hegel’s essentially Aristotelian conception of the state as the highest community, there arise immediately authoritarian, not to say totalitarian implications which are far removed from the essential liberalism of Hegel’s conception.

In light of the prevailing tendency to view the state as an ‘other’—an institution which is necessary, yet inherently alien to human beings—it is not surprising that Hegel’s meaning is obscured, and that some, like Russell, view the Hegelian state as one embodying the belief that true liberty consists in obedience to an arbitrary authority, that free speech is an evil, that absolute monarchy is good, that the Prussian state was the best existing at the time when [Hegel] wrote, that war is good, and that an international organization for the peaceful settlements of disputes would be a misfortune.

The Original Context: As the intellectual world has increasingly started reexamining the works of Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel one must recall that he was not just a great German philosopher but a major figure in European idealism. He was historicist and posited an idealist account of reality revolutionized the face of European philosophy and he was an important precursor to Continental philosophy and Marxism. Hegel developed a comprehensive philosophical framework, or "system", of absolute idealism to account in an integrated and developmental way for the relation of mind and nature, the subject and the object of human knowledge, psychology, the state, history, art, religion, and philosophy. In particular, he developed the concept that mind or spirit manifested itself in a set of contradictions and oppositions that it ultimately integrated and united, without eliminating either pole or reducing one to the other. Examples of such contradictions include those between nature and freedom, and between immanence and transcendence. Nevertheless, let me take this discussion on Hegel a step further by bringing it nearer home. In the process the concept of praxis a la Sadri is expanded and the concept of intensity a la Sharma is wedded into it.

Rene Descartes and linear logic: Two devout Christian scholars have charted two separate paths to arrive at logical solutions. The first scholar, (this paper will consider), is Rene' Descartes, a mathematician by training, and as we all know, gave the first formal proof of logic in his masterpiece *The Meditations*. Aiming to reach totally secure foundations for knowledge, he began to attack all his erstwhile beliefs with sceptical doubts. What was left was the certainty of his conscious experience and with it of his (own) existence. He posited a form of linear reasoning, which began, with a set of syllogisms ending in a conclusion, the whole of which being called an argument. A syllogism is a form of reasoning wherein a conclusion is drawn from two given or assumed propositions (premises). He stated that a middle or common term is present in both premises and it may even be invalid and is not present in the conclusion. He began by stating *dubito ergo sum*, (I doubt therefore I am) since the beginning of all inquiry and hence knowledge is doubt. He went on to posit his famous *cogito ergo sum*, (I think therefore I am), since our consciousness and self-realisation determines who (we see) we are. He ends his thoughts with *sum res cogitans*, (I am a thinking being), thus justifying the veracity of his argument. In mathematics, an argument is an independent variable determining the value of a function. For Descartes it symbolised either a reason advanced or the reasoning process itself. But we clearly need to go beyond the process, as the paper will argue.

What can be a better contradiction than a people voting a right wing government in India to power solely on the planks of inclusive developmental growth, minimum government and maximum governance? The failure of ideologies on the liberal centre and the left in India is writ large on the political horizon. People have unequivocally voted against more than a decade of scams, corruption, lethargy and false promises. The end of ideology, as Daniel Bell had argued, is nigh. The real politic of economic welfare that Sadri had exposed is now at hand.

Georg Hegel and the circular logic: Now we come to Georg Frederick Wilhelm Hegel.. Immanuel Kant had in his masterpiece *Critique of Pure Reason*, and then in *Critique of Practical Reason* attempted to classify the world leaving behind an essential dualism (a) nature opposed to spirit (b) object opposed to, and (c) the outer world composed of isolated unrelated substances. He created the real world where he placed human beings and the metaphysical world where he relegated God. It fell to Hegel's lot to reduce this duality to unity and he did this with majestic scholarship in *The Philosophy of History*.

Hegel posited a broad doctrine of freedom and saw two tendencies co-existing within objective social reality. Hegel saw this freedom through (a) unity of opposites (man usually marries a woman, a beautiful lotus blossoms in a dirty pond) and (b) viewed reality through contradictions (some are fair as others are dark; some are beautiful as others are ugly and some are tall as others are short). He consequently developed the dialectic further. The fact that the great Karl Max found Hegel standing on his head and proceeded to put him back on his feet is another matter, so we shall pass it by.

Hegel's logic or dialectic was fundamentally circular in contradistinction of Descartes's linear argument. The original thought was an idea, the most powerful thing (taking the queue from Voltaire). The opposition to it, as Hegel argued in *Phenomenology* was natural and finally (he prophesied) there would be a conclusion that is socially acceptable. In time this socially acceptable view would generate its own opposition and the cycle of thought (and action) would continue. Man, (the Bible says), was made in the image of God so for Hegel man was the original idea or thesis. Communal strife (man abusing his wife, wife beating the child, the child kicking the dog and the dog biting the neighbour) was the form which opposition to the original idea took and this was antithesis. This community had to be managed and Hegel's answer was the modern republic, the ultimate perfection that was his synthesis. As explained above, the thesis-antithesis-synthesis was a perpetual and cyclical phenomenon. We cannot forget that the republic of Thomas Hobbes was replaced by Abraham Lincoln's democracy.

Self-Righteousness and False Consciousness: The moral brigade across the world (unwittingly and invariably) uses the Cartesian argument. The crass misbehaviour of a policeman on the beat, for instance, with a well-known female model in Mira Road on the outskirts of Mumbai earlier this year being a case in point. The Press is inundated with similar incidents in Uttar Pradesh and Haryana where moral policing by the clergy and the Khap Panchayats are socially retarded, being blatantly anti-progress and anti-women.

The pseudo secularist opposition to a Uniform Civil Code has showed the shallowness of the argument. The comments made by certain sections of the clergy when the Supreme Court of India in July 2014 branded Sharia Law illegitimate and the attendant fatwas being illegal smacked of persons trying to impose 17th century morals on a 21st century populace (sic).

Invariably the proponents doubt the bonafides of a given action or scholarship think and believe that their own position or interpretation is correct and justify it by saying “we are right” as the religion or the custom or the belief system or our professional training has (somehow) ordained us to say so. ‘The hell with freedom of thought guaranteed by the Constitution; if we do not like it we shall create a ruckus and the docile / insecure / accommodative government will fearfully ban it.’ Salman Rushdie suffered in Satanic Verses because of multiple reasons principally being the appeasement of the vociferous sections in the Muslim community and was banned. David Laine and the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute (BORI) suffered a similar fate for the book Sivaji: Hindu King in Islamic India not too long ago. Surprisingly the “comrades” in West Bengal gave proletarian internationalism the short shrift to accommodate orthodoxy in the case against Tasleema Nasreen. Years ago, Dom Moraes could not publish his book since it carried a picture of the Parsee Tower of Silence and the self-styled interpreters of Zoroastrianism made quite a song and dance about it. That many Parsees outlive the vultures that feed on their carcasses is beside the point. Thank heavens people like Prahalad Kakkar and Soli Sorabjee stoically stood up and the Indian judiciary did not let the cause of scholarship down this time around. The more recent in the series of such steps was the police advice leading to the cancellation of a lecture scheduled by the Islamic Feminist Amina Wabud from USA at the University of Madras in the last week of July 2013. It is indeed a sad day for academia when what is to be discussed in the sanctum sanctorum of learning and knowledge is being dictated upon by law-keepers out of sheer fear of a handful of retrograde clergymen and their epigones. Fatwas of course will continue to come thick and fast from the disgruntled moral brigade on all sides of the ideological spectrum (mostly from the conservatives and the clergy not to forget the regionalists who hanker for the Muslim vote bank at any cost). The level of social consciousness of the populace will no doubt determine the efficacy of these fatwas. Why cannot these issues be reasonably and publicly debated? Why should we and how long should we succumb to the pressure of ill-tutored and ill-informed moral brigade. One could go on to even say willy-nilly that the 15th century Italian friar Girolamo Savonarola has been resurrected. So too, one often wonders why such an excellent rum Christian Brothers, suddenly went out of the market in Kerala or why nobody has filed a PIL to reconsider the parliamentary verdict in Shah Bano case? That the Congress Party that is clamouring for women’s rights today under Rahul Gandhi when the party had a clear majority in parliament under his father Rajiv Gandhi and yet took that retrograde step is nothing short of laughable. The more recent case of a young girl who was raped by her father in law and the Muslim clerics issued a fatwa asking her to ditch her husband in favour of his rapist father is clearly the repository and embodiment of all forms of soul destroying barbarism

Then some years ago there was the media hype surrounding Mandira Bedi’s sari flaunting the national tricolour below the knee or the not so recent brouhaha about Sania Mirza resting her tired feet next to the national flag! Lest we forget, in other countries people use the national flag as a bikini. Are these foreigners any less patriotic or are they being disrespectful to their country or their flag? One may seriously doubt it. Then why is all brouhaha this author wonders. Is it the moral brigade in a political garb that we see? All the author has to tell those “whose sentiments were (supposedly) hurt” by the lady’s sari is: for Heaven’s sake we should have please left that lady alone! Let the lawmakers concentrate on more important social issues like unequal distribution of wealth and incomes or the uneven development of communities and sectors. Ask questions like why was Quadrochi allowed to

flee India, why was the Purulia Arms Drop forgotten (until recently) and more currently why was the Deccan Herald Asset Grab Case not acted against suo motu? A major step would be for the Supreme Court of India to proceed suo motu against scamsters irrespective of their status or the political patronage they enjoy. Moreover, the author strongly opines those who feel that Indian (Hindu) culture is not liberated enough would be well advised to please start wearing a burkha or learn from a visit to the Khajurao temples. In either case, they will (hopefully) learn something.

More recently the civil society was “offended” by a vulgar adult comedy named AIB Roast and tried to make it an issue to be tried for criminal conspiracy. That the Indian to Censor Board initiated and went along with this self-righteous claim to come up with a list of 28 cuss words that could not be used in drama is nothing but the product of a sick mind.

The Indian Scenario: Lincoln at the Address given at the Gettysburg War Cemetery as had famously defined Democracy as the ‘government of the people by the people and for the people’. In a retarded peripheral capitalist economy, we need to ask ‘which people’? This is because practicing democracy on an empty mind and an empty stomach, (and we have plenty of those), is often and unrealistically asked. Just look at the definition of “poverty level” promoted by the Government whose own lawmakers roll in Crores! Sorry Dr Ranganathan !

Let us now take the Indian Constitution that is the foundation stone for our democracy, the rights of man and the division of powers, as a case in point. Our Constitution is a truly brilliant set of ideas, systems and procedures with commensurating rights and duties, conceived by great minds like Bhim Rao Ambedkar and Bhulabhai Desai and borrowed from the British and United States counterparts. These men were probably so high-minded that they just could not imagine that their grand schema could be corrupted and so did not place sufficient safeguards and deterrents in the Indian Constitution to prevent corruption being institutionalised. Hallowed ideas were continually shelved in the name of political expediency when lesser mortals became lawmakers. This phenomenon is by no means solely Indian and one can see it writ large in Africa, Latin America and Eastern Europe. Unwittingly perhaps successive political leaders have used it to create a micro-nationalism through the linguistic division of states and a macro-racism through a perpetual reservation policy. Nevertheless, the separation of powers between the legislatures the executive and the judiciary, though often brittle, is still holding out admirably.

Corruption, (defined as a deviation from the accepted norm), has not blunted the society entirely and we still have a few good men around who can and do make the difference. As a digression let me argue that if the “norm” itself is corrupt then how could one describe its correction and what could a few good men do? In foreign policy issues, we follow conventional wisdom, fraught with stupidity though it may be, when we write off 93,000 square kilometres of land to China that it illegally occupied in 1962 and then our Prime Ministers go to Beijing for bilateral trade talks! There is cross border infiltration by China since 2010 and yet our leaders visited that country and talked of peace.

However, let us not forget that the Constitution also creates a unity of opposites by bringing all religions under the banner of secularism. Secularism does not mean giving sops to the minority like writing off parts of the country like Kashmir or refusing to repeal Article 370 of the Constitution on flimsy rhetoric and outdated sentiments! Yet its usage sees reality in contradictions, when sixty five years after we gained our political independence, we still have a religion and caste based (rather than income based) reservation-quota policy! Why do some Indians believe that an Italian lady in the Nehru-Gandhi family at the helm can better guide the destiny of this country? It is bemusing that intellectually arrogant politicians defend this while laying claim to secularism. Hence, the first part of the Hegelian vision has been actualised.

It is to the eternal credit of Naveen Jindal who is an Indian politician and Member of Parliament (MP) from the Kurukshetra Lok Sabha constituency in the northern Indian state of Haryana who instigated an initiative that led to a revision of the Flag Code of India which now grants every Indian citizen the right to fly the Flag of India (also known as the "Tiranga") publicly with dignity and honour on all days of the year. But was this effort necessary? Does the government have the sole prerogative on nationalism? Are the only patriots to be found in the corridors of government? Can someone remind these political charlatans what Albert Einstein wrote in *The World As I See It* (1934): "Nationalism is an infantile disease. It is the measles of mankind." If you want to be nationalist then protect the nation first and hide behind politically motivated and often immoral rhetoric later. The likes of Omar Abdullah and Mufti Mohamed as well the pro-Pakistan fringe leadership in Kashmir are good examples of this phenomenon.

It is similarly a credit to the wisdom of Ratan Tata, then Chairman of Tata Group, to have pulled out the Nano car project from West Bengal and taken it to Gujarat because Mamata Bannerjee a local politician was too busy trying to score "brownie points" and chose to plunge the region into unemployment rather than to develop the state that had elected her. The socialist rhetoric flounders and the people bear the brunt of it. The people strangely still vote "left". History vouchsafes the fact that Indian Marxists often quote Lenin but seldom do they understand and practice Lenin. (Sadri 1999). We now know that Charu Mazumdar, Kanu Sanyal and the rest of the leadership of CPI (ML) had rushed into a "revolutionary mode" in 1967 when the subjective as well as the objective conditions for a revolutions just did not exist and sacrificed numerous lives in the bargain. This lesson seems to have been lost when decades later we see the myopia of leaders of CPI and CPI (M) and self-styled ideologues like Somnath Chatterjee, Prakash Karat, Sitaram Yechuri and the rest simply failing to see the mass movement of Anna Hazare of (2011) as a political opportunity and some of them went so far as to call it anti-national!. Such is the unity of opposites that stares us in the face.

The Dialectic of Article 370: Nothing seems to be more anachronistic than pseudo secularists defending the retention of Article 370. Simply put, Article 370 of the Indian constitution is a law that grants special autonomous status to Jammu and Kashmir. The article is drafted in Part XXI of the Constitution, which relates to Temporary, Transitional and Special Provisions a la Austin (1999). This article specifies that the states must concur in the application of laws, except those that pertain to Communications, Defense, Finance, and Foreign Affairs. By definition the Article grants special status to Jammu and Kashmir. Under Part XXI of the Constitution of India, which deals with "Temporary, Transitional and Special provisions", and as a result the State of Jammu and Kashmir has been accorded a special status. Even though included in 1st Schedule as 15th state, all the provisions of the Constitution which are applicable to other states are not applicable to J&K. For example, till 1965, J&K had a Sadr-e-Riyasat for Governor and Prime Minister in place of Chief Minister.

It is opportune to realize that similar protections for unique status existed in tribal areas of India including those in Himachal Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Andaman & Nicobar Islands and Nagaland. However, it is only for the state of Jammu and Kashmir that the accession of the state to India is still a matter of dispute between India and Pakistan still on the agenda of the UN Security Council and where the Government of India vide 1974 Indira-Sheikh accord committed itself to keeping the relationship between the Union and Jammu and Kashmir State within the ambit of this article. That India's sovereignty was sacrificed at the altar of political expediency in the case of Kashmir is well known to all modern historians.

Maj Gen Sheru Thapliyal writing in *Article 370: The Untold Story*, has dealt very lucidly with the intricacies and the genesis of article 370 and how Jawaharlal Nehru went to the extent of even telling a lie in the Indian Parliament. Why and how this happened is for historians to configure but for the purpose of this argument suffice it is to point out the supreme political contradiction where the Armed Forces Special Powers Act is the only saving grace for India's sovereignty. To appreciate the point being made a quick glimpse on what the Article in question entails is called for. Very briefly, the limitations from the Indian point of view are:

1. Jammu - Kashmir's citizens have dual citizenship.
2. The Jammu - Kashmir's national flag is different.
3. Jammu - Kashmir' Legislative Assembly's term is 6 years, whereas its 5 years for the States of India and there goes a uniform political system.
4. In Jammu - Kashmir it is not a crime to insult India's national flag or the national symbols!
5. The orders of the Supreme Court of India are not valid in Jammu - Kashmir.
6. The Parliament of India may make laws in extremely limited areas in terms of Jammu - Kashmir.

It is thus clear that these contradictions mounted on the platform of political expediency and given the pseudo garb of secularism are a ramification of a national sell-out. When we view this against the latitude granted to the Pakistan backed Jammu-Kashmir, some stark realizations spring up and these are:

- (a) If a woman marries a person of any other states of India citizenship to the female ends!
- (b) In contrast if a woman marries a person from Pakistan even that person will get citizenship of Jammu - Kashmir.
- (c) RTE is not implemented and RTI does not apply in Kashmir.
- (d) CAG does not have any jurisdiction and Indian laws are not applicable.
- (e) Sharia law is applicable to women in Kashmir so gender based oppression is legalized.
- (f) There are no rights to panchayats in Kashmir and local self-government has a new and anti-India meaning.
- (g) A peon only gets Rs 2500 in Kashmir since the Minimum Wages Act does not apply.
- (h) Minorities in Kashmir [Hindu - Sikh] do not get 16% reservation while India claims to be a nation state with a secular base.
- (i) Outsiders cannot own land in Kashmir and thus the suzerainty of a “democratic” India takes hike.
- (j) Very strangely, Pakistanis get Indian citizenship, for which they only need to marry a girl from Kashmir. Hence infiltration (Jihadi or otherwise) gets a legal mandate.

From an essential political economy perspective this paper raises some ancillary issues by way of some self- evident questions regarding Jammu and Kashmir in the post 1947 era. The intention is demonstrate that these Hegelian reality in contradictions are inimical to social economic and political progress and interests of the very people they are meant for. It will similarly help to highlight how Indian interests have been sacrificed by Indian politicians for self-serving and minimalist interests and hence demonstrate a unity of opposites.

- (i) Is there any statistical record regarding the number of Pakistanis marrying Kashmiri girls to become Indian Citizens?
- (ii) How many Kashmiri girls have sacrificed (and also willing to sacrifice) their dual citizenship by marrying an Indian?
- (iii) How many Indians (military + civilians) have sacrificed their lives for keeping Jammu & Kashmir with India?
- (iv) Has the quantum of subsidy being paid to maintain status-quo vis-a-vis the contribution of Jammu & Kashmir towards Indian economy ever been calculated and made public?
- (v) Giving freedom to the people of Kashmir is fine but will the Kashmiris, ever be able to maintain independence (imagining that they get one!) against Pakistani aggression, single handed?

Perhaps the time is ripe for having an open national debate, keeping the emotions to the minimum on the futility of trying to withdraw the Armed Forces Special Provisions Act up until the time that Article 370 stays. Then again the repeal of AFSPA is not an emotional issue as is often claimed. Rather it is a strategic and fundamental issue linked with our sovereignty which requires that AFSPA be retained at least for some more time. The fact that certain (self-styled) Political Pundits are still clamouring for status quo on the Jammu and Kashmir issue while insisting that India talks to the separatists and repeal AFSPA could easily border on treason and this is something we need to introspect on. Nevertheless this remains a classic case of Hegelian contradiction.

Hegelian Change: Now we come back to the Hegelian dialectic of thesis-antithesis-synthesis. It is well known that political, social, cultural and economic decisions are taken with the vote bank in mind. Common good and with it the common person is sidelined at best and his interests are consigned into the trashcan of social history at worst. The thesis prior to 1945 was a unified India, which we now call the Indian sub-continent. The antithesis after 1947 saw the creation of India and Pakistan from the earlier geophysical mass. This antithesis continued up until 1971 when Bangladesh was created and liberated from Pakistan. Then we had the synthesis, with the creation of the ASEAN. In a decade's time this synthesis became the thesis. Now with the breakup of a composite India into smaller the antithesis has already set in.

It is well known that the Anglo-US combine divided the Indian Subcontinent into Burma, Nepal, Pakistan and India to avoid a huge land mass that could have linked up with Iran and given access to oil. On the other hand, they did not want such a land mass going over to Stalin. Hence they made sure that the twin evils of micro nationalism (as in the linguistic division of states) and macro racism (as in the reservation policy) were perpetuated by the new neo-colonial regime of Nehru and his epigones, This ensured that real unity of people was kept in abeyance.

Neo colonial control of the economy via the under developed agricultural sector was ensured first through the PL480 scheme and later through genetically engineered seeds. How else can we justify the fact that more than 60% of the 1.4 billion strong populace depends on the primary sector while 53% contribution of the GDP comes from the tertiary (services) sector? Hence, this synthesis is in itself fractured.

This neo-colonial false consciousness permeates civil society even today, more than six decades later, when self-styled activists harp on what the constitution guarantees them but are dangerously silent on the duties expected by the same constitution from an Indian citizen. So too human rights activists who go on a "dharna" to protect the rights of terrorists but have nothing to say of the infringement of human rights for the innocent victims of the terrorist's bomb attack.

Political contradictions: How long and how well this new synthesis will last was a moot point since it had started to generate itself into a thesis after Indian became a part of the WTO Regime. I opine with the benefit of foresight, that what happened in 1947 and the resultant disintegration of an undivided India in the light of what is happening today was a good thing after all. Beginning with Jawaharlal Nehru and the eviction of Kashmiri Hindus from the homeland, the policy of appeasement has continued unabated reaching ridiculous heights. We are all aware that during his tenure as the Governor from 1984 to 1989, militancy in Jammu and Kashmir was at his peak and he was credited with providing capable administration to the state. In Jammu & Kashmir, Jagmohan is credited for bringing order to one of the most revered shrines of Hindus, called Mata Vaishno Devi. He also created a board that continues to provide administration for the shrine. Infrastructure was developed and that continues to facilitate pilgrims. However, what we seem to conveniently forget is that it was (allegedly) under Jagmohan acting at the behest of Rajiv Gandhi that panic spread among Hindus in Kashmir and the ill-advised Diaspora from Kashmir to Jammu took place. What is happening, for instance, in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar is alarming. Political hooliganism in the name of protecting minority rights is rampant. Misbehaviour of politicians with civil servants doing their duty is well known as is the use of state agencies like the CBI against political opponents by the Central Government in the pre-2015 era. The Kashmiris as usual when pushed into a corner were playing the secessionist card when Abdulla (father and son) said that if Narendra Modi won (as he did) Kashmir would not be a part of India any more. The point at issue is that a temporary reprieve given under the Nehru Government through Article 370 has clandestinely been converted into a constitutional right by the Muslim majority in Kashmir and their cohorts in the “nationalist” parties like the Indian National Congress, the Samajwadi Party and a few fringe players. The reluctance of Mamata Banerjee, of Sharada Scam fame, to evict Bangladeshi refugees who are a potential vote bank and the “solidarity” of Tamil parties in India with the Tamils in Sri Lanka rather than with their motherland is sadly ironical.

Issues like caste and religion have taken precedence over issues of education and development for the past decades. Rhetoric has replaced action and the populace has been taken for a ride. Secularism is term often mouthed by some political parties to act as a cover for garnering the minority vote bank by fair means or foul. The passiveness and inability of the Indian Government to protect the interest of Kashmiri Pundits remains a black spot on the Indian claim to secularism and has taken the wind out of the sails of successive governments in Kashmir. Is it not an anachronism that Muslims still want to be treated as minority in spite of the growing numbers and demographic volumes? Why did it take someone like Najma Heptulla in 2014 to correctly point out that the Muslim claim to minority rights since 1954 was farcical?

One still remembers that the barrage of attacks on Narendra Modi for not being secular enough comes from the very political arena that had orchestrated the anti-Sikh riots in Delhi when Indira Gandhi died in hail of bullets just because the assassin was a Sikh. One can harass an honest man but not defeat him as was evident when the “snoop gate” case was withdrawn by the Central Government in the dying days of UPA II. The vitriolic speeches of Imam Bukhari and the diatribe of Azam Khan (of lost buffalos fame) or Omar Abdullah and his father Farooq Abdullah are not a defence of minority rights (as is claimed) but a sick attempt to use the secular card to remain in power. When Priyanka Gandhi talked of being honest when her hubby Robert Vadhra was caught in the cross hairs of a land grab scam is laughable. So was the case when Rahul Gandhi had claimed to be interested in developing a constituency that he likes to be elected from in Uttar Pradesh and where he was conspicuous by his absence over the past decade defies logic. The public acceptance of this fact by the Indian National Congress too defies logic and exposes the hollowness of political leadership.

In Bihar Nitish Kumar had upped his ante after years of sharing the political bed with BJP just because they are not secular enough for him! This if nothing else exposes the hollowness of claims of pseudo-secularism which is a new avatar of political opportunism. Laloo Yadav also misbehaves at the toll gate with government officials when his wife Rabri Devi is caught carrying cash (during a random check) above the permissible limit during election time

not too long ago. In the midst of such behaviour any claims of us being fair, democratic or cultured fall flat on their face. Contradictions are thus writ large on the face of the polity. Mamata Banerjee issues ration cards to illegal Bangladeshi refugees in exchange of votes just as the father and son Yadav duo in Uttar Pradesh is busy placating Muslim vote bank and turning a Nelson's Eye to rising crime. Alliance of non BJP regional players is very much on the cards as the Congress would (ostensibly) not hesitate to share the podium with anyone who can further their political ambitions – damning the ideology.

The fact that a two centres of power arrangement in Delhi has miserably failed is evident. The Office of the Prime Minister had been reduced to a rubber stamp for the Gandhi family over the last decade is well accepted. That an economist like Manmohan Singh should have used quasi Keynesian ideas to prop up Fiscal and Monetary policy while eulogising the virtues of Monetarism and Supply Side Economics is hard to digest and needs to be treated with disdain. As this author have elsewhere stated, there is too much politics with our economics and too little economics with our politics, and this is a fact that has been proved beyond doubt over the past decade. Is the populace really better off as high unemployment figures indicate? Contradictions are thus writ large on the face of the economy.

Protagonists may even say that had India been undivided, the populace from Bangladesh and Pakistan with the Indian Muslim would have swamped the polity and socio-economic policies (following the idea of appeasement) would have made the Hindus a minority in their own country! The Hegelian synthesis would have become the new thesis for pseudo-secularism awaiting perhaps a (violent) antithesis to continue the cycle. Secularism (in its retarded form) is being defended by spreading the fear of new (imagined) Jihadi like holocausts against the smaller minorities like the Parsees, the Jains, the Bohris, the Bahaiis and the Christians could have happen if parties espousing Hindutva came to power! This is but the harangue of a sick mind and disastrous faction of polity that is willing to damn the nation only to secure its personal future. Let us understand that Hinduism is not a religion but a way of life that has tolerantly assimilated cultures and peoples from all over through time immemorial. Hence, to this author the very idea of a Hindu terrorist or a Hindu holocaust is an oxymoron.

Conclusion- Going beyond Descartes and Hegel:

Contradictions in the Indian polity and the accompanying centrist ideology are thus rife. Papa Hegel looking down on Mother Earth from Heaven, (for he was a devout Christian and knowingly did no wrong), would be dancing with glee. This would occur whenever he would train his celestial binoculars on India, (after a tipple that he liked), and if only because this is one country that has proved the old philosopher to be indubitably correct after all.

REFERENCES

1. Ackrill, J L (1981): Aristotle the Philosopher, Oxford, Oxford University Press.
2. Acton, H B (1955): The Illusions of the Epoch, London, Cohen and West.
3. Althuser Louis (1976): Essays in Self Criticism, London, New Left Books
4. Arendt, Hannah (1958): The Human Condition, Chicago, The University of Chicago Press.
5. Austin, Granville (1999). Working a Democratic Constitution - A History of the Indian Experience. New Delhi: Oxford University Press
6. Bell, Daniel, (1988): The End of Ideology, Cambridge Mass, Harvard University Press.
7. Berger Peter, (1977): Pyramids of Sacrifice, Penguin, Harmondsworth.

8. Berger Peter and Luckmann, Thomas, (1971): The Social Construction of Reality, Penguin Harmondsworth.
9. Berlin Isiah, (1955): Against the Current, New York, Viking Press.
10. Camus Albert (1956), The Rebel New York: Random House,
11. Chomsky Noam (1993), Year 501: The Conquest Continues (Montréal, New York: Black Rose Books,
12. Copleston, Frederic S J (1946) (1950) (1953): The History of Philosophy in three volumes, New York, Doubleday.
13. Dahrendorf, Ralf (1968): Values and Social Science: the value dispute in perspective
14. Descartes Rene' (1965): A Discourse on Method and Other Works, New York, Washington Square Press.
15. Durkheim, Emile (1950): The Rules of Sociological Method, Chicago, Chicago Press.in Essays in the Theory of Society, Stanford California, Stanford University Press
16. Durrani, Tehmina (1998): Blasphemy: a novel, New Delhi, Viking for Penguin Books.
17. Eagleton, T. (1996): The Illusions of Postmodernism, Oxford, Polity Press
18. Engels, Frederick (1975): Ludwig Feuerbach and the End of Classical German Philosophy, Peking, Foreign Languages Press.
19. Foucault, Michael (1971): Madness and Civilisation: A History of Insanity in The Age of Reason, London, Tavistock Publications.
20. Friedrich Carl J, .(1953) The Philosophy of Hegel New York: Modern Library,.
21. Freire, Paolo (1970): The Pedagogy of the Oppressed, New York, Continuum Books.
22. Golding, Martin P (1975): Philosophy of Law, Engelwood Cliffs N J, Prentice-Hall.
23. Goodrich Carter L (1975): The Frontier of Control, London, Pluto Press.
24. Gorz, Andre (1982): Farewell to the Working Class, London, Pluto Press
25. Habermas, Jurgen (1976): Legitimation Crisis, Cambridge, Policy Press.
26. Hazlitt, Henry (1959): The Failure of the New Economics, Amsterdam, Van Nostrand
27. Hegel, G F W (1953) (1988): Reason in History, (Reprint), London, Macmillan.
28. Hegel, G F W (1956): The Philosophy of History, New York, Dover Publication.
29. Hegel, G F W (1952, 1967)The Philosophy of Right (T.M. Knox, ed.; London, Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press,

30. Hobbes Thomas, (1968, 1985) Leviathan (C.B. Macpherson, ed.; Harmondsworth, Middlesex, England: Penguin Books
31. Hobhouse L T (1921), The Metaphysical Theory of the State (London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd.
32. Illych, Ivan (1973): De-schooling Society, Harmondsworth, Penguin.
33. Jayashree S and Sadri S (1998): Managerial Leadership in the Twenty First century, Vision, Vol 2, No 1.
34. Kant, Immanuel (1936): Critique of Pure Reason, (Reprint) London, Everyman's Library.
35. Kant, Immanuel (1980): Critique of Practical Reason, Indianapolis, (Reprint) Bobb – Merrill Educational Publishing.
36. Lenin, V I (1938): Materialism and Empiro Criticism, New York, International Publishing Co. Inc
37. Malinowski, Borislav. (1982): Magic Science and Religion, and other Essays, London, Souvenir Press.
38. Mautner, Thomas (2010) Dictionary of Philosophy Penguin Books, New Delhi
39. Marcuse, Herbert (1941) (1960): Reason and Revolution, Reprinted Boston, Beacon Press
40. Mills C Wright (1970): The Sociological Imagination Harmondsworth, Penguin.
41. Nandy, Ashish (1994): The Illegitimacy of Nationalism, New Delhi, Oxford University Press.
42. Peel Peter (1982) Preface to Alfred Rosenberg's Myth of the Twentieth Century (Vivian Bird, trans.; Torrance, California: Noontide Press, (, xxvii.
43. Popper Karl Raimund, (1968) Conjectures and Refutations: The Growth of Scientific Knowledge (New York: Harper & Row,
44. Prahalad C K and Lieberthal K (2003): The End of Corporate Imperialism, Harvard Business Review, August.
45. Radhakrishnan S (1974): The Dhammapada, Madras, Oxford University Press.
46. Radhakrishnan, S (1976): The Bhagavad Gita, Calcutta, Blackie and Son.
47. Rawls, John (1971): The Theory of Justice, Cambridge Mass, Harvard University Press
48. Rushdie Salman (1988): The Satanic Verses, Harmondsworth, Penguin.
49. Russell, Bertrand (1927): The Future of Science, London, Kegan Paul, Trench Tubner.
50. Russell, Bertrand (1930): The Conquest of Happiness, London, Routledge.
51. Russell Bertrand (1950), Unpopular Essays (London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd
52. Sadri S and Hegde D S (1993): The Liberalised Economy and The Corporate Manager The Economic Times, 22 July.

53. Sadri S and Hegde D S (1993): The Liberalised Economy and The Corporate Manager The Economic Times, 22 July.
54. Sadri S (1999) Approaches to International Economic Analysis and its implications for Indian Socialism, in Asian Economic Review
55. Sadri S and Tara S N (2012) India as a Future Superpower: conjectures and refutations, International Journal of Economics and Business, Vol 11, No 2
56. Sadri S (2012) Reservation Policy and Macro Management of Human Resources in India, IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, (Poland) summer
57. Sadri S (2012) The Realpolitik of Economic Welfare [Observations on Democracy, Arrow's Impossibility Theorem and The Paretian Liberal Paradox in the Indian Context] Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development Vol.3, No.2,
58. Sadri S and Tara S N (2014) Future Trends in Indian Education Text of Invited Paper at IMS Ghaziabad on 30.11.2013 published in Reinventing Management Strategies in Marketing and Finance, Edited by. Urvasi Makkar, Vijay Kumar Pandey, Rinku Sanjeev, and Rajnesh Jain, Bharati Publications, New Delhi 2014
59. Sadri S (2014): Crisis in the Capitalist Periphery: the case of South East Asia and Lessons for India, International Journal of Marketing and Financial Management (2348-3954 on line), Vol 2 Issue 2, March
60. Sadri S (2014) Globalization Revisited International Journal of Latest Technology in Engineering, Management & Applied Science-IJLTEMAS, Volume III Issue VII August
61. Sehgal, Narender (1994). "Chapter 26: Article 370". Converted Kashmir: Memorial of Mistakes. Utpal Publications Delhi: Retrieved 17 September 2013.
62. Sharma Subhash. (1996): Management in New Age: Western Windows Eastern Doors, New Delhi, New Age Publishers
63. Thapliyal Maj Gen Sheru (2014) Article 370: The Untold Story <http://www.indiandefencereview.com/news/article-370-the-untold-story/>
64. Toynbee, Arnold (1934 - 61): A Study of History (12 Volumes), London, Oxford University Press.
65. Voltaire (Francois Marie Arouet) (1964): Philosophic Dictionary, quoted in Lord Morley: Voltaire, London, Foreign Classics for English Readers Series.
66. Weber, Max (1930): The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism, London, (Translated by Talcott Parsons), George, Allen and Unwin.
67. Weber, Max (1932): The Theory of Social and Economic Organisations, Fair Lawn, N J., Oxford University Press.